

Design and Application of Affinity Systems in Biomedical Problems*

P. K. BHATTACHARYYA, C. V. NATARAJ, (Mrs.) CHITRA MANDAL and YOGAMBAL SRINIVASAN

Department of Organic Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore-12

and

M. DEVANANDAN,

C. M. C., Vellore

The precision of mutual recognition of biomolecules has been defined in terms of free energy release in the associative process. Among the factors contributing to the energy release hydrophobic associations involving the homomeric (D-DL) or (L-L) and enantiomeric dimerisation (DL) of amino acids substituted by the hydrophobic group and a marker group which reports about the nature of the environment has been delineated.

The use of affinity chromatography based on specific recognition has been illustrated in three biomedical problems. In the first example a specific penicillin carrier receptor protein (CRP) has been isolated both from normal rabbits and those immunized with penicillin as well as from normal and penicillin sensitive human subjects by affinity chromatography on synthetic polymers containing the structural elements of benzyl penicillin. The polymer HF 3 in which the carboxyl end of benzyl penicillin was linked to polymeric benzyl alcohol yielded the electrophoretically homogeneous rabbit anti penicillin IgG (M.W. 150000, Heavy Chain M. W. 50,000, Light Chain M. W. 23,500) antibody by sequential elution with 0.9M thiourea after a salt wash (0.75M). The covalently bonded rabbit carrier receptor protein (CRP) in the fully antigenic penicilloylated conjugate form was detached from the polymer by the hydrogenolysis of a benzyl ester linkage. The penicillin free-CRP could be isolated in 8M urea wash from a polymeric template containing 7-deoxy benzyl penicillin (7-DOHF 3). The rabbit CRP (M. W. 60,000) combined with $^{14}\text{-C}$ benzyl penicillin in 1:1 stoichiometry. Equilibrium dialysis and fluorescence quenching experiments with $^{14}\text{-C}$ -7-deoxybenzyl penicillin gave an equilibrium constant of 2.1×10^6 /mole with a ΔG of association of -8.1 Kcal/mole and $K 2.8 \times 10^6$ /mole respectively. With benzyl penicillin the total activation free energy was of the order of $\Delta G + 13.26$ Kcal/mole. Fluorescence quenching studies also revealed two conformational changes of CRP in penicillin binding—one fast folding corresponding to the non-covalent binding of 7-deoxybenzyl penicillin to CRP and a slow unfolding corresponding to the covalent binding of 6-amino-penicillanic acid to CRP.

Several analogues of penicillin showed stronger binding to CRP than benzyl penicillin in competitive binding experiments. Compounds with negatively charged groups at α -position or o -position in the side chain showed stronger binding while those with positively charged groups were weak binders. It was possible to construct an outline of the penicillin binding cleft in CRP.

The antipenicillin rabbit antibody bound CRP penicillin conjugate with a stoichiometry of 1:2 with a ΔG of -12.02 Kcal/mole. Competitive binding studies of CRP-penicillin-G and analogue conjugates showed that the CRP-conjugates of some of the strong CRP binders, such as those of methicillin and o -nitrobenzyl penicillin are very weak binders with the antibody.

Affinity chromatography of M 13 coliphage infected *E.coli* cell constituents of polystyrene on *E.coli* lipopolysaccharide template and on a DNA-Sepharose template resulted in the isolation of the M 13 gene 2 product in the pure form and it was possible to establish for the first time the endonuclease activity of this protein.

By using a strychnine-Sepharose template it was possible to purify the strychnine-specific rabbit antibodies raised against strychnine-bovine serum albumin conjugate. The purified antibodies after labelling with fluorescein isocyanate revealed the strychnine binding sites on post-synaptic motoneuron membranes from monkey spinal cord.

CHEMISTS have been familiar with the term "affinity" for several centuries until the end of the nineteenth century the term "valence" was introduced. This term takes care of all instances where covalent or ionic bond formation takes place. However, the term "affinity" is still necessary to cover the entire range of weak interactions where subsequent co-valent bond formations may or may not be involved.

These non-covalent weak interactions in the "affinity" processes assume tremendous importance in biological systems. To illustrate the point a steady state inventory of the microbe *E. coli* would show several thousand polymers such as proteins, nucleic acids, polysaccharides, several thousand simpler organic molecules which are substrates for enzymes and about 20 inorganic ions within the cell envelopes, where there are no

* Sir J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture for 1975 delivered at the Annual Convention of Chemists, Jaipur on 24.12.77 by Dr. P. K. Bhattacharyya.

specific barriers to their movement. Yet the functioning of the cell depends on very specific recognition of substrate molecules by corresponding enzymes. The precise nature of this specificity can be appreciated from the fact when DNA is synthesised only the deoxy ribotrinucleotides are recognised by the DNA polymerases, excluding the rather abundant pool of ribotrinucleotides such as ATP to build new strands on the complimentary template. On the other hand, when messenger RNA is synthesised by RNA polymerases on the same DNA strand as template, not a single deoxy ribonucleotide is introduced.

Since it is not permissible to seek Divine Intervention or a Maxwell's Demon in this selection, one has to explain the specificity as well as the speed of the mutual recognition in terms of statistical mechanics and thermodynamics.

In a highly simplified model let us consider a molecule AB which can attach itself to two specific sites of a macromolecule (active site of enzyme for instance) X and Y. Let E_x and E_y be the release of energy of association of AB with the points X and Y and K_x and K_y be the rates at which AB associates with these points X and Y.

Since the Arrhenius equation for the total chemical reaction is also valid for the individual steps, it must hold true in the attachment of the molecule AB to sites X and Y prior to any chemical reaction.

Thus for the site X,

$$K_x = A_0 e^{-\frac{E_x}{RT}}$$

and for the site Y,

$$K_y = A'_0 e^{-\frac{E_y}{RT}}$$

where A_0 and A'_0 are Arrhenius constants defining the cross-section and orientation of the collision process, an identical operation.

By choosing the group at X and Y to be the same and, alignment of AB at sites X and Y to be identical,

$$A_0 = A'_0$$

The relative rates of AB going to sites X and Y would then be,

$$\frac{K_x}{K_y} = e^{-\frac{(E_x - E_y)}{RT}}$$

Taking logarithm to the base 10 at 300°K and $R = 1.98$ cal/ mole/degree,

$$\log \frac{K_x}{K_y} = \frac{-(E_x - E_y)}{2.3 \times 1.98 \times 300} = \frac{-(E_x - E_y)}{1400} \text{ approx.}$$

If $-(E_x - E_y)$ is only 1400 call/mole or 1.4 Kcal,

$$\log \frac{K_x}{K_y} = 1 \text{ or } K_x = 10 K_y.$$

A small difference of energy release of 1.4 Kcal in AB-X combination over AB-Y would thus mean that AB would be propelled 10 times faster towards site X.

When equilibrium is reached and the release of all other forms of energy besides that free energy are ignored, we have

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K.$$

With a ΔG difference of -1.4 Kcal/mole it can be shown that at equilibrium 90% of the time an AB molecule would be at site X and 10% of the time at site Y.

In the biological systems three main interactions may lead to the energy release :—(1) Ionic interactions, (2) Hydrogen bonding and (3) Hydrophobic associations. Of these the first two interactions are better understood, but the hydrophobic interactions are not easily amenable to study as they arise from the release of bound water structures on the surface of hydrophobic groups. The organization of the bound water leads to a loss of entropy and thus the energy release in hydrophobic association is entirely derived from entropy.

1. Hydrophobic Associations :

There are several theoretical and experimental approaches to estimate the energy of hydrophobic associations^{1,2,8} (and the references therein). In our laboratory we employ a direct method^{4,5} which is outlined as follows⁴. If one puts a hydrophobic group (Hyd) and a marker group (M) (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1

which gives information about the environment on an asymmetric carbon containing two other oppositely charged groups (for example, an amino acid at isoelectric point) and consider the modes of self association of the D or L as well as enantiomeric association of DL pairs one finds that in D-D (or L-L) association of type I is not possible as it places two similar charges in juxtaposition. Dimerization is possible by rotating one of the molecules by 109° in which the marker group (M) of one of the molecules is on the hydrophobic group of the other as in II. It is, however, possible to build polymeric clusters of D-molecules in which the hydrophobic groups are aligned with the charged portions in two molecules oriented towards opposite direction but unless the hydrophobic association energy is very large, at least -8 Kcal/mole the dimerization as in II would be the favoured mode of association.

In the case of DL pairing however III is the ideal energetically favoured association having the hydrophobes aligned and opposite charges paired at the other end leaving the marker (M) in the free water.

The methodology, therefore, is to start with 100% of one isomer D or L, and to add increasing concentration of the other enantiomer and monitor the information based on the marker group M. To illustrate the point in the homomeric (IV) and enantiomeric dimerization (V) of α -methyl α -*p*-nitro-glycine at isoelectric point in water in D-D pair (IV) the marker group (methyl) shows an upfield shift in p-m-r spectra, being in the shielding zone of the aromatic π electrons where as in the DL pair the aromatic protons undergo downfield shift, each being distinguished by the aromatic ring.

Therefore, by measurement of the observed chemical shift of either the methyl protons or the aromatic protons in graded concentrations of D and L isomers it is possible to calculate the equilibrium constant and the free energy difference between *p*-nitrophenyl and methyl association by the following relationship

$$\delta_{\text{obsd}} = \frac{L_T - x}{L_T} \times \delta_L + \frac{x}{L_T} \delta_{DL}$$

where δ_{obsd} is the observed chemical shift of the proton signal of the mixture and δ_L and δ_{DL} are the chemical shifts of the same protons of free L and pure DL respectively. L_D , D_T and X represent the molar concentrations of pure L, D and pure DL complex respectively at equilibrium.

The equilibrium constant K is given by

$$K = \frac{[x]}{(L_{DT} - x)(L_T - x)}$$

and the free energy of association by $\Delta G = RT \ln K$.

Calculations with the *p*-nitrophenyl, methyl glycine system give with K 40 mole $^{-1}$ and $\Delta G = -2.1$ Kcal/mole for mutual association of *p*-nitrophenyl groups over that of *p*-nitrophenyl methyl association in water.

The ΔG of association of two phenyl groups in water has been calculated from the decrease in UV absorbance at 271 nm in the DL mixture as compared to that in pure L in D and α -phenyl glycine as -3.4 Kcal/mole.

For the determination of hydrophobic association energy of non-aromatic hydrophobes the same technique can be employed employing c-m-r shifts. However, the poorer solubility of these amino acids at iso-electric point in D_2O is a major unsolved problem.

While the compilation of a set of numerical values for the different hydrophobic group is a time-consuming process, the existence of high degree of affinity as evinced by very selective recognition of one biomolecule by another can be a highly productive occupation of chemists particularly synthetic organic chemists. We will endeavour to illustrate the approach by summarising our work in three different biological problems.

II. Chemical Approaches to Penicillin Allergy :

A. Isolation of a penicillin Carrier-Receptor Protein and antipenicillin antibody.

The antigen-antibody interactions are generally characterized by a high degree of specificity. We had chosen to work on the problem of penicillin allergy because of the importance of the problem. Various demographic estimates show that roughly about 3-5% of the population in any part of the world show some reaction to penicillin. In most cases the reaction is mild such as itching or inflammation at the injection site or mild urticaria or a just feeling of uneasiness. Only 0.01 to 0.02% of these sensitive subjects show severe reactions such as anaphylaxis or death.

The mechanism of allergenesis follows the broad pattern of immunogenesis. An antigen which is recognised by the body as a foreign body enters the lymphatic system and excites certain immunocompetent cells, "B" cells and "T" cells or other cells. The antigen recognises the cell by complementarity or affinity through some surface structures (surface antibodies). These cells after differentiation produce the antibody proteins which are of five major classes, IgG, IgD, IgA, IgM and IgE. Of these IgG is mainly a humoral antibody and circulates in the blood stream. The reaginic IgE antibodies generally responsible for allergy are, on the other hand, picked up by different cells and lead to cellular sensitization. Only a small amount of IgE is released in the blood.

The nature of penicillin antigen is still subject to controversy. Stewart *et al*⁶ believe that these antigens may be proteinaceous or polymeric impurities in commercial penicillin preparations which escape purification, whereas Levine and others are of the view that penicillin itself can react with some plasma protein and the conjugate may trigger the immunogenetic reactions. Levine^{7,8} advanced the viewpoint that a reactive molecule such as penicillin may react with a protein in the sera of sensitive animals or humans to constitute an antigenic molecule with penicilloyl moiety as the haptenic group (BPO-antigen).

Our work in this field is based on the assumption that both viewpoints may be true—a penicilloylated polymer of extraneous origin or one derived *in vivo* may function as the penicillin antigen and build up antibody response, whether reaginic or non-reaginic. In the animal body one requires a highly specific penicillin carrier-receptor protein (CRP) to build up molecule of antigenic dimensions. To be considered to be a carrier receptor the protein must have the following characteristics :—

A. Among plasma proteins it must bind with penicillin most strongly and possibly covalently.

B. The conjugate of this protein should be an antigen and react with antipenicillin antibody.

C. The molecular weight of such protein should (but not necessarily) be above 20,000.

To trap the carrier receptor protein two types of affinity polymers were synthesised^{5,9} (Fig. 2). (1) The tail-free polymers TF-1, TF-2 and TF-3 had the carboxyl end of benzyl penicillin free and connected to the polymeric backbone of polystyrene with spacer atom chains of 0.5, and 7 atoms between the haptenic group and the backbone.

(2) The "head-free" polymers HF-1, HF-2 and HF-3 having the phenyl end of benzyl penicillin free was linked through the carboxyl end through a benzyl ester linkage separated by 0.5, 7 atoms from the polymeric backbones.

The synthesis of these polymers have been described elsewhere^{5,9}.

The HF-3 polymer gave the best performance regarding the adsorption and elution of both the antibody and the CRP⁵ and used for further studies.

Rabbits immunized against penicillin and Freund's adjuvant for 10 weeks showed haemagglutination titres of 640-1280 dilution units^{5,9,10}. The sera was fractionated with the polymer HF-3 according to the scheme shown (Fig. 3).

FRACTIONATION OF SERA ON HF-3 A 7-DOHF-3 POLYMER

Sera (5 ml) in pH 7.2 phosphate buffer saline PBS (0.05M, 10 ml) stirred with HF-3 (DOHF-3) polymer (5g) filtered.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

The 0.9M thiourea fraction containing an electrophoretically homogeneous protein⁹⁻¹² M. W. 150000 (SDS gel) which consisted of two types of subunits (M. W. 50000 and 23500) could be easily identified as the rabbit IgG anti-penicillin antibody by haemagglutination. The hydrogenolysate from the polymer HF-3 gave a single band in disc electrophoresis¹⁰ and was identified as the CRP-penicilloyl conjugate as it reacted with the antibody as an antigen. Since this protein (a) associated with the penicillin template in the polymer more strongly than any other protein in the sera, (b) it was covalently bonded to the polymer and (c) reacted with antibody in the penicilloylated form obtained through hydrogenolysis, it satisfies all the criteria of the hypothetical-CRP. The mode of its binding to the polymer and its release is depicted in Fig. 4.

ADSORPTION

Fig. 4

Unfortunately, from the polymeric HF-3 penicillin template the CRP was obtained as the conjugated penicilloylated derivative as the full fledged antigen by the design of the experiment itself. But to conduct the kinetic studies on penicillin binding and to develop anti-penicillin allergic drugs, the unconjugated penicillin-free CRP had to be isolated. For this a polymer template containing 7-deoxy analogue benzyl penicillin lacking the reactive β -lactam carbonyl which is responsible for binding with the protein was prepared (Fig. 5). The synthesis of 7-deoxybenzyl penicillin was achieved for the first time taking advantage of the very fast reaction rates of disubstituted amides with diborane on 6-carbobenzoyloxy-6-aminopenicillanic acid benzyl ester. After removal of protective groups 7-deoxy-6-amino penicillanic acid was acylated with phenyl acetyl carbinol and connected to the polymer to give the 7-deoxy HF-3 polymer^{5,11} (Fig. 5).

SYNTHESIS OF 7-DEOXPENICILLIN AND POLYMER

Fig. 5

From the 7-DOHF-3 polymer the antibody was obtained as usual in the 0.9M thiourea fraction and the free CRP in the 4-8M urea fraction in the sequential elution scheme (Fig. 3) in electrophoretically homogeneous form. The CRP did not react with the antibody as such but did so after incubation with penicillin^{5,11,12}.

The human CRP was isolated from both normal and penicillin sensitive human subjects by identical affinity chromatographic technique and was found to have a molecular weight of 43,000^{11,12}.

It was found that CRP concentration in normal unimmunised rabbits varied from 12 to 96 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ in the sera and these levels increased with the progress of immunization^{11,12}. Rabbits with higher CRP responded faster to penicillin and built up higher antibody titres. In limited samples of sera from normal human subjects the CRP was of the order of 20-30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and a sensitive subject had more than 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ¹².

CRP is, therefore, a constitutive protein in the sera. It may also have other functions also besides combining with penicillin.

The antibodies raised in rabbits by immunization with penicillin alone and those elicited with a prepared benzylpenicilloyl bovine serum albumin conjugate had identical properties and electrophoretic mobility. This indicated that both the types of antigen derived extrinsically or intrinsically in the animal body may give rise to identical or very similar antibodies^{11,12}.

B. Binding studies with CRP and benzyl penicillin and analogues :

Having achieved the purification of both the

components of antigen antibody reaction it was possible to estimate the binding parameters with haptenic systems. By employing ^{14}C -benzyl penicillin prepared from ^{14}C -carboxyphenylacetic acid it was possible to estimate the stoichiometry of penicillin binding as 1 : 1^{12,13}. Since the binding of benzyl penicillin is irreversible and covalent, the equilibria and free energy changes were estimated in the first instance with ^{14}C -7-deoxybenzyl penicillin prepared from ^{14}C -carboxyphenyl acetic acid and 7-deoxy-6 APA. Two techniques were used in determining the thermodynamic parameters—(1) equilibrium dialysis and (2) fluorescence quenching. The equilibrium dialysis experiments gave linear Scatchard plots (Fig. 6) and the CRP-7-deoxy

Fig. 6

benzyl penicillin (DBP) reaction was shown to be of first order with respect to both CRP and DBP (Fig. 7). Fluorescence quenching studies indicated that the reaction proceeds with a conformational change as evidenced by both hypochromic and bathochromic shift (Fig. 8). The equilibrium constant K was determined by both methods were close to each other. $K = 2.8 \times 10^6$ mole and 3.6×10^6 with a ΔG of approx. -8.1 Kcal/mole and -8.9 Kcal/mole respectively^{12,13}.

Fluorescence quenching studies on benzyl penicillin and CRP reaction revealed two conformational changes, (1) a fast one corresponding to the non-covalent binding of 7-DBP with CRP, and (2) a slower one accompanied by a small hypsochromic shift (Fig. 9) which corresponded with the binding of 6-amino penicillanic acid with CRP (Fig. 10). The fast change of 7-DBP binding which was not

Fig. 7

observed in the case of 6-APA and the kinetic data reflected the covalent interaction only with a pseudo-first order rate constant of 1.4×10^{-3} /min. Since the competitive experiments to be discussed later showed that 6-APA is a stronger binder than benzyl penicillin for the CRP cleft, it was concluded that the 6-APA binds to the CRP initially without

Fig. 8. 1. CRP only
2. 0.03 ml Deoxybenzyl penicillin
3. 0.05 ml "
4. 0.07 ml "
5. 0.11 ml "
6. 0.16 ml "
7. 0.24 ml "
8. 0.40 ml "

any conformational change followed by covalent-linkage formation which is reflected in the fluorescent quenching experiments (Fig. 10). The total activation free energy of penicillin G binding to CRP (non-covalent and covalent) was estimated to be $\Delta G^+ - 13.26$ Kcal/mole.

Fig. 9. 1. CRP only 2. CRP+PG 0 min.
3. CRP+PG 60 mins. 4. CRP+PG 120 mins.
5. CRP+PG 200 mins. 6. CRP+PG 280 mins.
7. CRP+PG 360 mins.

Fig. 10. 1. CRP only
2. CRP+6 APA, 0 min.
3. CRP+6 APA, 60 mins.
4. CRP+6 APA, 120 mins.
5. CRP+6 APA, 200 mins.
6. CRP+6 APA, 280 mins.

Competitive binding studies for various analogues of penicillin were conducted with different molar

Fig. 11. 1. Carbenicillin ; 2. 6-Aminopenicillanic acid ;
3. Ticarcillin ; 4. Amoxycillin ;
5. Ampillin. Thick Diagonal-penicillin.

Fig. 12. 1. Methicillin ; 2. O-Nitrobenzyl penicillin ;
3. O-Aminobenzyl penicillin ; 4. 7-Deoxybenzyl penicillin.

proportions of the analogue concerned and ^{14}C -benzyl penicillin and estimating the undialyzable radioactivity associated with the CRP in presence of analogues. Figs. 11 and 12 represent the data. The diagonal line, represents the data for benzyl penicillin and several other analogues which bind with the same energy as with penicillin with CRP.

The curves above the diagonal represent the weak binders and those below indicate stronger binding.

The order of binding of various analogues and derivatives of penicillin is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. Order of binding of penicillin Analogues to Rabbit Carrier Receptor Protein (CRP).

By superimposing Drieding models of these analogues with the β -lactam thiazolidine occupying the same site one can roughly construct the CRP cleft in two dimensional space^{13,18}. Three of the analogues methicillin, cloxacillin and benzyl penicillin are represented in Fig. 14. It may be noted from Fig. 13 that alteration at the thiazolidine end of the penicillin molecule do not materially affect the binding ability. Benzyl penicillin has been reduced to a primary alcohol group or 3-desacetoxy-7-phenylacetyl cephalosporanic acid (benzyl cepham) in which the thiazolidine ring has been expanded to a six-membered dihydrothiazine ring system having approximately the same affinity as benzyl penicillin with the CRP. Probably this once again falls outside the CRP cleft—a conclusion also indicated by the direction of trapping of CRP on the 7-DOHF-3 polymer. Changes in acyl groups, however, influence the binding of the analogues. In the cleft space (Fig. 14) one can locate the nucleophilic amino group which reacts with the β -lactam carbonyl and a positively charged group such as $-\text{NH}_3^+$ near the α -region of the side chain making carbenicillin and *o*-nitrobenzyl penicillin a better binder than benzyl penicillin, ampicillin, amoxycillin and *o*-amino benzyl penicillin poor binders to CRP because of charge-charge interaction and repulsion respectively. Since, amoxycillin is a better binder than ampicillin one can postulate the existence of an electronegative group at the deepest point of the cleft forming hydrogen bond with the *p*-hydroxy group. However, the location of the

THE PENICILLIN BINDING CLEFT OF CRP

--- METHICILLIN ; — BENZYL PENICILLIN ; == CLOXACILLIN

Fig. 14

group is such that a linear hydrogen bond is not possible with a *p*-amino group. Otherwise groups at para position in the aromatic ring have no influence on the binding to the CRP cleft. The strong binding of methicillin and cloxacillin is due to a closer steric fit in areas ahead of the α -region. The only anomalous case is that of the 6-unsubstituted 6-APA. The strong binding suggests that the molecule may possibly be reversed inside the cleft presenting the carboxyl group to the electropositive site of the $-\alpha$ -region^{12,13}.

The antibody of the IgG class was found to be divalent by binding studies with ¹⁴C-penicilloyl CRP-conjugate^{12,14}.

The equilibrium constant of the antigen-antibody interaction was shown to be $K=2.6 \times 10^9$ litmole⁻², $\Delta G = -12.02$ Kcal/mole, $H^{\Delta H} = +360$ Cal/mole⁻², $\Delta S = 30$ cu/mole by filtration, through millipore which retains the complex but allows the antigen and the antibody to pass through.

Competitive binding studies with the antibody and conjugates of the different analogues of penicillin in presence of ¹⁴C-penicilloyl CRP-conjugate in millipore filter assay revealed the order of binding as shown in Fig. 15.

Fig. 15.

It may be seen that only the complex of the CRP with 7-DBP had stronger affinity for the antibody site than benzyl penicilloyl CRP. All other conjugates showed weaker binding than the penicilloylated CRP, methicillin, ticarcillin and *o*-nitrobenzyl penicillin did not compete at all with the benzyl penicilloyl-CRP for the antibody site.

If one assumes that for penicillin allergy cases the best strategy would be to look for an analogue which binds with the CRP strongly, and sequesters the CRP but the conjugate would not interact with the antibodies, the rabbit model indicates experiments with methicillin or *o*-nitrobenzyl penicillin in human cases.

The antigen antibody binding is an intriguing topological problem. The CRP has to engulf the penicillin molecule and to re-expose the moiety as a haptenic group for antibody binding. The strong affinity for the antibody for the HF-3 and 7-DOHF-3 polymers also indicate the hapten-specific sites on the antibody. The situation is illustrated in Fig. 16. Here the case of 7-deoxy penicillin which does not form a covalent band with CRP is an enigma.

Fig. 16. Schematic representation of formation of Penicillin Antigen and Antigen-Antibody recognition.

The studies conducted with rabbit CRP and antibody are being extended further with the human CRP and antibody. The entire breakthrough has been possible because of affinity chromatography which in one single operation gives two pure vital protein components in which chemical *in vitro* experiments are possible without elaborate animal experiments. Having a knowledge of the topology of the CRP-cleft permits us to design with a certain degree of precision of drugs which may be a better potential applicability in penicillin allergy.

We will now illustrate the use of affinity systems in two other areas of biomedical research to bring out the versatility and power of the technique.

II. Isolation of Gene 2 product of Coliphage M 13 :

M 13 belongs to a unique group of small single stranded DNA bacteriophages. The peculiarity of M 13 is that it does not kill the host *E. coli* cells : Generally M 13 is male specific believed to be absorbed through the sex pilli along with the protein coat. After infection—a complementary strand of DNA is built around the viral circular DNA—the RF form which is nicked on one strand to give RF-1, the replicative form and multiple copies are produced. After maturation, the membrane properties of the host change with the release of outer membrane lipopolysaccharide and the phages containing one of the single strands within a protein coat ooze out of the host cell membrane.

Fig. 17

The M13 DNA M. W. 1.2×10^6 is known to contain about 10 cistrons or genes. The gene II is particularly interesting, as mutations in this gene blocks three functions in the phage life cycle—replication of RF, host permeability changes and lipopolysaccharide release. It has been suspected earlier that the gene II protein has endonuclease activity to convert the circular RF to the nicked RF-1 form for replication¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

Earlier attempts to show the endonuclease activity failed as the gene II protein separated by the sodium dodecyl sulphate gel electrophoresis could not be renatured effectively.

We anticipated that in order to release lipopolysaccharides and to nick circular DNA the gene II protein may have affinity for both. Two types of affinity systems were prepared : (1) a polystyrene based *E. coli* lipopolysaccharide template and (2) double stranded DNA-sepharose template.

E. coli lipopolysaccharide was prepared according to literature¹⁴ grafted on to the polymer using the sequence in Fig. 17. For DNA-sepharose the CNBr activated sepharose was coupled with double stranded calf thymus DNA.

Adsorption of sonicates of *E. coli* cells infected with wild type M 13 phage on the polystyrene-LPS system was followed by sequential elution with 0.5M saline phosphate buffer pH 7.0, 0.9M thiourea and 8M urea. The 0.9M thiourea eluate showed four distinct fractions in polyacrylamide gel disc electrophoresis of which the topmost band (slowest moving) was absent in the sonicates of uninfected cells and those from permissible (K37) cells infected with amber mutants of gene II¹⁸. Mutants in

Fig. 18.

Fig. 20

Fig. 19

other genes such as am5 also had this protein. The other three bands due to host membrane proteins were present in all cases.

TABLE 1—RADIOACTIVITY BOUND TO MILLIPORE FILTERS AFTER TREATMENT OF 10 l. of 3H PHAGE DNA (10,000 cpm) WITH M 13 GENE II PROTEIN AND REMOVAL OF UNBOUND MATERIAL

M 13 gene II protein (100 g/ml) in l.	Counts retained on filter (cpm)
5	2,500
10	2,400
20	2,480
—	1,000

The gene II product was located in tubes No 20-24 by comparing the chromatographic behaviour on DNA-sepharose column of the sonicates from cells infected with the wild type M13 and those with the amber II mutant (Fig. 18). Since it

is known that infected cells at 42° produced more of the gene II product¹⁹ by temperature shift experiment this identification was confirmed (Fig.19). The pooled 20-27 fraction was chromatographed on a Sephadex S-100 column (Fig. 20) and then purified. Electrophoretically homogeneous preparation was tested for endonuclease activity by two methods using radioactive RF DNA :— (a) retention of nicked DNA on millipore filter and (b) release of radioactive TCA-soluble nucleotides from the nicked DNA by exonuclease which does not act on intact circular DNA. The results presented in Tables 1 and 2 show feeble but unmistakable endonuclease activity of the purified gene II product¹⁸.

TABLE 2—PERCHLORIC ACID SOLUBLE RADIOACTIVITY RELEASED AFTER TREATMENT OF 10 l. OF 3H PHAGE DNA (10,000 cpm) WITH M 13 GENE II PROTEIN FOLLOWED BY *E. COLI* EXONUCLEASE I TREATMENT

M 13 gene II protein (100 g/ml) in μ l.	Exonuclease I (1 mg/ml) in l.	PCA soluble radioactivity (cpm)
5	10	2,100
10	10	2,115
20	10	2,000
—	10	500
10	—	500
—	—	600

III. Location of strychnine-binding sites on post synaptic muto-neuron membrane :

It is now generally accepted after Curtis' elegant work²⁰ that the alkaloid strychnine blocks the sites

for glycine, a negative neurotransmitter, on the motoneuron membrane. This causes firing of the synapse and the strychnine administered animals ultimately go into convulsions. In collaboration with the Department of Neurophysiology at the Christian Medical College, Vellore we have been able to locate the strychnine binding sites on post synaptic spinal cord membrane using affinity chromatography and fluorescent labelling^{19,21}.

(Pt 1, left-hand side). The membrane from a normal monkey did not show the spots (Pt 1, right-hand side).

The above examples would amply demonstrate the power of the technique of affinity chromatography. The specific functionalisation of drug molecules and the construction of affinity templates are newly emerging challenging areas for the Organic Chemist.

Fig. 21

Strychnine was functionalised to 3-amino strychnine through the 3-nitro derivative. 3-Amino strychnine was diazotised and coupled to bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Fig. 21) and antibodies were raised against the strychninised protein. These antibodies were purified by titration with polymeric BSA which removed the BSA specific antibodies and then through the affinity templated constructed from Sepharose and amino-strychnine (Fig. 22).

Fig. 22

The purified antibody showing a single band in disc electrophoresis was labelled with fluorescein by coupling with fluorescein isocyanate.

By applying the labelled antibody on to motoneuron membrane prepared from spinal cords of strychninised monkeys the strychnine-binding spots could be located through fluorescent microscopy

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to CSIR for a Silver Jubilee Grant and to DST for grants to support the work and Junior Research Fellowships to C. V. Nataraj and Chitra Mandal.

References

1. W. KAUFMANN, *Adv. Protein Chem.*, 1959, **14**, 1.
2. C. TANFERD, *Adv. Protein Chem.*, 1970, **24**, 1.
3. G. NEMETHY and H. A. SCHEREGA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **36**, 3382.
4. P. K. BHATTACHARYYA, C. V. NATARAJ, B. G. NIRANJAN and J. N. JACOB, *Ind. J. Phys. Commemorative Volume*, 1977, 213.
5. C. V. NATARAJ, Ph. D. Thesis "Physico-chemical Interactions on synthetic templates", Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, 1975.
6. G. T. STEWART, *Lancet*, 1967, **I**, 1177.
7. B. B. LEVINE, *J. Exp. Med.*, 1960, **112**, 1960.
8. B. B. LEVINE *Nature* (London), 1960, **987**, 1960.
9. P. K. BHATTACHARYYA, C. V. NATARAJ, D. R. RAO, S. P. BHATNAGAR and S. P. PAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 122.
10. P. K. BHATTACHARYYA, C. V. NATARAJ, A. ROY, S. P. BHATNAGAR, D. R. RAO and S. P. PAL, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 1975, **62**, 153.
11. C. V. NATARAJ, CHITRA MANDAL, and P. K. BHATTACHARYYA, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1978, **87A**, 1.
12. CHITRA MANDAL, and P. K. BHATTACHARYYA, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1978, **87A**.
13. CHITRA MANDAL and P. K. BHATTACHARYYA, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1978 (In Press).
14. L. G. CARO and M. SCHNOIS, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. U. S.*, 1966, **56**, 126.
15. W. OLSSALIVAR, H. TZAGOLOFT and D. PRATT, *Virology*, 1954, **24**, 359.
16. D. PRATT, *Ann. Rev. Genet.*, 1969, **3**, 343.
17. R. E. WEBSTER and J. S. CASHMAN, *Virology*, 1973, **55**, 20.
18. Y. SREENIVASAN, Ph. D. Thesis, Physico-chemical Interactions on Synthetic Templates, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, 1977.
19. T. J. HENRY and D. PRATT, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. U. S.*, 1969, **62**, 800.
20. D. R. CURTIN, *Progr. Brain. Res.*, 1969, **15**, 185.
21. J. D. MARSHALL (Jr.), W. G. EVELAND and C. W. SMITH, *Proc. Soc. Experi. Biol. & Med.*, New York, 1959, **98**, 1959.